

A NEW SHORT HISTORY OF PHOTOGRAPHY: GERALDO DE BARROS AND THE HOMAGE TO PAUL KLEE

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SUMMARY

In *Homage to Paul Klee*, 1949, Geraldo de Barros goes beyond the idea of a tribute to invent a technical combination in photography that includes aspects of printmaking and painting as well as a liberated imagination. This image, part of the *Fotoformas* series from 1949, marks a mile-

stone in the history of photography, as it introduces a novel procedure invented by de Barros. In summary, this essay examines the transition from “homage,” understood as recognition, to an artistic procedure in de Barros’s work through this technique.

A genuine homage from one artist to another occurs when the former benefits from what the latter’s work offers. Paul Klee’s work opened a toolbox of imagination for Geraldo de Barros, allowing him to refine his photographic invention with engraving and painting techniques. In this regard, T. S. Eliot’s words in “Tradition and the Individual Talent” resonate: “Tradition is a matter of much wider significance. It cannot be inherited, and if you want it you must obtain it by great labour.”¹ De Barros worked hard to internalise what he learned from Klee. Therefore, the first way to introduce *Homage to Paul Klee* is through a photograph from 1949 that is part of the *Fotoformas* series (FIG. 1). This photograph, which could be compared to Brassai’s works about anonymous graffiti, stands apart because de Barros doesn’t just record the reality present on a city’s walls. Instead, he intervenes in the negative, using engraving techniques to draw an irregular head with a dry point and ink. In this photograph, by making an

uncanny creature, de Barros not only relates it to Klee in terms of the drawing content but also emphasises the lightness of the line, highlighting how holes, marks, and traces on the photographed wall that served as a starting point for a print obtained through an artistic intervention on the negative. Inside the section of the drawing, where he portrayed a head, the area of the wall is clearer than the one outside the figure. The soft contrast in the image is a feature of the strict control of the photographic process, which result in different levels of light on a single image. This homage involves an admiration exercise helping to adopt artistic procedures associated with Klee. His way of conceiving a photograph would be enough to assure de Barros a singular place in the global history of photography or in a new short history of photography.

In 1931, when publishing the essay “A Short History of Photography,” Walter Benjamin emphasised that, for centuries, people sought to fix images produced by the camera obscura, a feat only achieved

Fig. 1
Geraldo de Barros, *Homenagem a Paul Klee (Cabeça de menino)*, 1949/1977, photograph, drawing on negative with dry point and India ink (vintage print), 29.8 x 33.0 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, donation from the collection of Fabiana de Barros & Michel Favre, Geneva © Instituto Moreira Salles / Geraldo de Barros
Image credit: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

in the 19th century by Niépce and Daguerre. It wasn't until the early 20th century that photography assumed artistic prominence within the avant-garde, breaking free from merely capturing reality. Photography had to seek an autonomous artistic status to move beyond the servant representation of reality. Maintaining the path of a new short history of photography, Geraldo de Barros's work proposes a new chapter, where his works are part of the historical succession of inventions in the history of the medium in Brazil. In this new short history, the focus lies on de Barros's photographs, which, in the mid-20th century São Paulo, ventured into the

invention of the life of forms, with Klee playing a relevant role. Klee was a black box for de Barros, enabling the transition of techniques from printmaking to photography while also allowing the artist's imagination to concretely develop a conception beyond the act of taking pictures. Thus, in this case, influence does not assume a hierarchical value; rather, it operates in a field where works dialogue, clash, and converge.

To continue this new short history, it is necessary to contextualise *Fotoformas*, the series to which the photograph belongs. Although the series began in 1948, the title only came later, in 1950, during

ongoing experiments at the collective laboratory of the Foto-Cine Clube Bandeirantes. As Sarah Hermanson Meister pointed out regarding the Foto-Cine Club Bandeirantes (FCCB): “For many years following World War II, photographs by FCCB members were an integral part of a dynamic international network of exchange.”² Usually, the FCCB members shared the same darkroom and rationally divided the few photographic materials available in the city. Due to the high costs of materials, Geraldo de Barros’s photographic experimentation was understood as an expense that should be rationally used to obtain an excellent photo by compositional means, such as adjusting focus, defining the subject, exposure, and perspective, to name a few of them.

Despite being marginalised by the FCCB direction, which sought to equate photography with visual representation, de Barros persisted in laboratory techniques, making photos beyond a click. His intuition guided his explorations of compositions that lay between the photographic moment and the development of each image. In photography, he also found a lesson in painting and printmaking, implying a back-and-forth movement within the image, concretising abstractions that modified and reached specific compositions in *Fotoformas*, whose exhibition followed on January 2, 1951, soon after the series began, at the Museum of Modern Art in São Paulo (MASP). Before departing for Europe the same year, de Barros left his experiments documented in the exhibition. As the director of the MASP, Pietro Maria Bardi, wrote in the presentation of his work, his abstract signs were fanciful and Olympian. With that, de Barros captured the spirit of the signs in urban space introducing them to more geometrical signs in photography. The figure itself is not abolished but rather invites geometrical perception into abstraction and the concrete value of the signs.

In this sense, de Barros contributed to the development of post-photographic photography within a collaboration between abstraction and concrete art in Brazil. In terms of camera techniques, he mastered the camera and demonstrated this still in *Fotoformas*. He wanted to invent a different photographic path. This decision was so important that his photographic work laid the foundations for abstractionism and concrete painting in Brazil. Sarah Hermanson Meister highlights that “in de Barros’s practice, and in Brazil more broadly, abstraction in photography anticipated abstraction in painting.”³ The *Fotoformas* series forms the foundation of this development, connecting de Barros’s Brazilian experiences with avant-garde practices. Even in *Painting, Photography, Film*, published by László Moholy-Nagy in 1925, there isn’t such an advanced level of experimentation. Undoubtedly, *Painting, Photography, Film* contributed to a critique of photography and anticipated experiments like those by de Barros: “We must be prepared for this,” wrote Moholy-Nagy, “but we have hitherto been too fully prepared [...] [with] formal tensions, penetration, chiaroscuro relationships, movement, tempo.”⁴

In the late 1940s and early 1950s, everything de Barros absorbed in terms of theories, especially *Gestalt*, exhibition visits, readings, or interactions with other artists was channelled into *Fotoformas*. This dedication became his unique form of thought: more than thinking through images as a result of what he was seeing, Geraldo de Barros thought in terms of procedures and abstractions. The photographic technique was a mobilising force, especially in the darkroom, as photography became a gravitational centre once its broader functionality was integrated into his practices.

Another way to describe de Barros’s photographic awareness could be what Rosalind Krauss proposed with sculp-

ture – photography in the expanded field.⁵ Although this statement might seem modest, Geraldo de Barros's strength lay in separating photography from the camera, challenging pre-programmed gestures within the act of shooting. The camera is not the unique guardian of photographic art. Moholy-Nagy had already recognized the photogram, and in the immediate post-war redefinitions of art, Krauss sought to understand sculpture within a redefined context, hence proposing its expansion. Geraldo de Barros expanded photography beyond the photographic act and the photogram. Another factor playing an important role in the development of the *Fotoformas* series was the implementation of punched cards in computing systems, such as those used in the bank, bank where de Barros was working. Having observed the rhythm of this machine codification, de Barros took useless punched cards into the photo darkroom, giving the cards a new use in introducing abstraction into the photographic language.

The *Fotoformas* series represents a milestone, a dividing line between the research de Barros conducted in Brazil and what he would later confirm and deepen during his travels in Europe with a French government scholarship in 1951. Still, Klee continued to influence his imagination, as de Barros noted in a late 1970s statement: "Around 1948, I became interested in Klee and completely immersed myself in his influence. I wanted to know his techniques and how he approached his work. At that point, Livio Abramo greatly helped, teaching me the technique, showing me how Klee resolved his works."⁶ The idea conveyed in this statement is that an artist responds to the challenges that art itself presents. In this sense, Geraldo de Barros sought an intense dialogue with Klee's work.

It should be noted that prior to any tribute, when an artist engages with an-

other's work, there is a vital need to understand how that work can be resolved. This involves externalizing the internal mechanisms that animate it. For Klee, this could mean the movement of lines in the spatial dynamic between Earth, Water, and Air, for Geraldo de Barros, it means the movements of light regarding the ways of cutting off from the space of its reference. Both artists perceive this in terms of energy circulating in their drawings, paintings, and, in de Barros's case, photographs. But the issue is not limited to composing lines or light: both share a graphic, visual thought that goes beyond the visible. The fact is that for both, each image does not depend on the visible to exist, and they stressed the forces that make an image visible. For Klee, this involves the circulation of energy, air, and space – especially the space that mediates the relationship between "I" and "you," a dialogue with nature (FIG. 2).⁷ Here, the image is a matter of addressing, and the artist, still according to Klee, is nature. The most important thing on this approach is that the artist looks for relationships with the optical and physical qualities. The image is the air. Still, Klee added layers of air to his images that play a fundamental role in visibility. For de Barros, instead, light becomes a centre of forces where modulations emerge in the form of painting, printmaking, photography, or furniture. These forms engage in dialogue with a plurality of relations connected with *Gestalt*, which is also a way of thinking that form is not only a pure formalistic gesture but plays a role regarding the nature of the image. Nothing is more concrete to him than abstraction, which implies affirming a photographic operation in the expanded field, considering that *Fotoformas* align with the artist's fundamental principles in photography.

Through a slow and varied process, Geraldo de Barros worked to make Klee his precursor, especially in terms of pro-

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Fig. 2
Paul Klee, *Theory of Pictorial Configuration: Attachment* (illustration of "Paths in the Study of Nature"), pen on paper on cardboard, 33 x 21 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, inv. no. BG A.030
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

cedures or technique, as de Barros previously defined it. In *Schöpferische Konfession*, Klee surprisingly asserts that the purer a graphic work becomes, "the more emphasis is given to the formal elements underlying graphic representation, the more inadequate the preparation for the realistic representation of visible things."⁸ There is a performative contradiction between the graphic representation and the representation of visible things, because escaping realism wasn't just Klee's goal,

as he focused on linear, planar, and spatial modulations and energies, as if he acted sensitively following the principle of X-rays with his engravings and paintings. With that, he created infragrams of the natural world by intervening in reality, as described in "Wege des Naturstudiums":

"Yesterday's approach to art and the associated study of nature consisted, one might say, of embarrassingly differentiated investigations into appearances. I and you, the artist and his subject seek relations through the optical-physical path via the air layer between me and you. In this way, excellent surface images of the air-filtered object were obtained, and the art of optical vision was expanded, compared to which the art of seeing and making visible non-optical impressions and ideas remained neglected."⁹

In taking Klee's position, Geraldo de Barros concentrated techniques from printmaking and painting in photography. With the camera, he photographed detailed image overlays on a single frame. The exposure could have been made multiple times during shooting or afterwards. In this sense, the exposure time of a negative in the darkroom means that light is a phenomenon that must be rigorously controlled. If we were to paraphrase Klee's text to interpret de Barros's photos: the artist and his urban subject seek relationships through optical-physical paths via the luminous forms that exist between the world and the camera, deepening the light realities, the nature of the signs, or how one form come from the other. Here, three different fields are together: phenomenology, semiotics, and morphology. In that sense, he photographed the limits of photography, exploring where its boundaries could be.

Geraldo de Barros was not fully satisfied with this mediated relationship through the camera. For him, photography was more than a fleeting surface image. Even at the beginning of his experi-

mentation in 1948, what interested him was the entirety of the process – image development, print intervention. Whether by cutting the negatives or using punched cards that marked the beginning of computerized bureaucracy in institutions such as the Brazilian Public Bank where he used to work, Geraldo de Barros cut, rearranged, and then placed the result between glass plates to make a photo. With one foot in the legacies of *Fotoformas* and the other foot in the future – after all, *Fotoformas* is contemporary, both present and future, as are the other photos in this series that stand up today. Therefore, by relating it to Klee, this photograph from 1949 was not just a tribute to him; de Barros also linked his artistic future to a visual thinking that stems from and advances beyond abstraction. Thus, as Eliot wrote: “What happens when a new work of art is created is something that happens simultaneously to all the works of art that preceded it.”¹⁰ By delving into Klee’s work, de Barros becomes part of a chain of future creation, where the toolbox of abstraction continues to be opened. This is how a “short history of photography” starts a new chapter.

Geraldo de Barros understood the photographic act beyond the “decisive moment,” as defined by Henri Cartier-Bresson, who emphasized the moment when the camera, photographer, and subject align in the composition of an image. De Barros approached photography through the reality of the darkroom, making it his *camera obscura*. Even though pictorialist photographers of the late 19th and the early 20th already had a similar approach to photography, by painting on negatives and combining multiple exposures, Geraldo de Barros’s photographic practice contributes to the rise of a new level of experimentation in photography not only in Brazil, but in postwar photography worldwide. In a 1977 interview, he stated, “For me, photography is a print-

making process.” He added, “If retouching is allowed, then alterations to the negative are also permissible. A found negative, scratched and dusty, if it provides a good photographic result, belongs to the one who creates the photograph, not to the one who exposed the negative.” This definition still expands the concept of photography, shifting the “decisive moment” to the moment of enlarging the negative, i. e., to a decision made in the darkroom.

“THE ORDINARY INVISIBLE”: THE DIALECTICS OF ABSTRACTION ACCORDING TO GERALDO DE BARROS

Some years are decisive for artists. That was the case for Geraldo de Barros at the end of the 1940s. 1949 was a prolific year for him, and still according to Pietro Maria Bardi, who was the director of the MASP, “Geraldo focuses on certain aspects or elements of reality and, especially, on details that are ordinarily invisible.”¹¹ With *Fotoformas*, the negative presented many material possibilities for composing an image: it could be painted, drawn upon, cut, and even reassembled. One example is urban signage that, instead of indicating directions, draws attention to itself and to the autonomy of photography. This is also evident in photographs from the same period, which were enlarged from negatives cut and pressed between two glass plates.

Another photograph from the *Fotoformas* series, *The Girl and the Shoe (A menina e o sapato)*, 1949, takes another direction. Starting with a photograph of a shoe, the artist intervenes on the negative using dry point and India ink, transforming a single shoe photographed from above into a mouth for the drawing created by the artist. This photograph represents a dialectical point between figuration and abstraction, which extends into the artist’s experiments with *Gestalt* and the simultaneous combination of expressionism and

concrete art.¹² However, when discussing de Barros's works, one must be cautious in distinguishing where abstraction and concreteness lie, as Walter Zanini noted in a brief article published on March 8, 1953:

"At the beginning of 1952, Geraldo was already back [in Brazil]. He then began making concrete photographs. He abandoned photography made with a camera, creating photograms by recording with light. He considered the camera a compromise with figuration. He explains the difference between abstract and concrete photography: 'If we manage to focus on details that no one knows what they are, we are faced with abstract photography. When we organize forms in space, we are in the field of concrete photography.'"¹³

For Geraldo de Barros, abstraction is a dialectical exercise with material concreteness in terms of realization. This suggests that abstraction is not just a space devoid of figuration but a qualitative leap in terms of the signs that emerge from photographic procedures. As de Barros himself stated:

"To abstract means, for me, in photography as in painting, to create abstract forms, to create signs, a language in which reality no longer figures. In any case, I am obliged to photograph something, but that something, I transform it according to my will, according to the means, balances, and rhythms, to make a plastic composition where the subject is entirely forgotten, absorbed."¹⁴

The negative, a singular piece in analogue photography, loses its uniqueness: scratched, drawn upon, painted, cut, and assembled, it generates a new original. Rhythm is a central term that Geraldo de Barros connects with the work and thought of Paul Klee. Photography becomes a heterodox space where technique and imagination align, allowing figuration and abstraction to continuously interact. "With Klee, Geraldo learns an

artistic practice in which technique is both an effort of formalization and a stimulus for imagination, and there is no opposition between abstraction and figure, but a continuous oscillation."¹⁵ This positions Geraldo de Barros as one of the most inventive artists of the transition from the first to the second half of the 20th century. His graphic reasoning leaps from painting to photography and extends to objects, doing so in an integrated manner. But if photography absorbs other techniques, it is because, for de Barros, it presents itself as an expanded field for all the arts and is not limited to the camera.

If the artist skilfully navigated the intermediate zones between image and object, "intersection" is a key term for understanding his photographic practice. Beyond the biographical principle that divides the artist's life into phases or periods, one can assert that de Barros mastered the art of finding refuge for photography in intermediate spaces between painting, printmaking, objects, and even furniture. De Barros founded two collective furniture design ventures: Uni-labor, which operated from the early 1950s until the mid-1960s and weakened after the onset of the military dictatorship in Brazil in 1964, and *Hobjeto*, which followed in the 1960s and continued until the mid-1980s. In these two initiatives, Geraldo de Barros aimed to make modern furniture more accessible, successfully reinventing domestic and workspaces with a language that remained connected to photography, painting, and printmaking.

In 1987, Eugen Gomringer, in a brief presentation of Geraldo de Barros, discussed a dual play of two German concepts that fit de Barros's work: the first is "Gestalt," and the second is "objective design language" ("objektive Designsprache"), highlighting the anonymous adventure of the object and, therefore, its mobility.¹⁶ From this perspective, the distance between photography and furniture

diminishes, as de Barros's work can be understood as a complex of modules where everything fits together. He furnishes our modern imagination, escaping more stable categorizations in terms of constructivism, formalism, abstraction, etc. But through their anonymous heroism, objects gain circular vitality in societies, even through images. From this perspective, photography carries a set of relationships: between the arts, between objects and referents, and between referents and the new realities that are established. Through this dialectic of abstraction, Geraldo de Barros materializes a new stage in a small history of photography. We could attribute to this new small history a keen gaze that does not necessarily stem from an abstract reference. While Klee helped de Barros to open the doors of imagination and technique in the field of photography, the fact is that *Homage to Klee* being part of the collection at the Zentrum Paul Klee does not fail to pay homage to Geraldo de Barros.

¹ Eliot 1919, p. 55.

² Hermanson Meister 2021, p. 12.

³ Ibid., pp. 16–17.

⁴ Moholy-Nagy 1969, p. 34.

⁵ Kraus 1979.

⁶ Barros 2022, p. 208.

⁷ Klee 1923, p. 24.

⁸ "Je reiner die graphische Arbeit, das heisst, je mehr Gewicht auf die der graphischen Darstellung zugrunde liegenden Formelemente gelegt ist, desto mangelhafter die Rüstung zur realistischen Darstellung sichtbarer Dinge." Klee 1920, p. 28.

⁹ "Die Art des Kunstbekenntnisses von gestern und des damit zusammenhängenden Studiums der Natur bestand in einer, man kann wohl sagen peinlich differenzierten Erforschung der Erscheinung. Ich und Du, der Künstler und sein Gegenstand suchten Beziehungen auf dem optisch-physischen Weg durch die Luftschicht, welche zwischen Ich und Du liegt. Auf diesem Weg wurden ausgezeichnete Bilder der von der Luft gefilterten Oberfläche des Gegenstandes gewonnen und damit

die Kunst des optischen Sehens ausgebaut, gegenüber welcher die Kunst des Betrachtens und des Sichtbarmachens unoptischer Eindrücke und Vorstellungen vernachlässigt zurückblieb." Klee 1923, p. 28.

¹⁰ Eliot 1919, p. 56.

¹¹ Hermanson Meister 2021.

¹² Bandeira 2022.

¹³ Zanini 1953.

¹⁴ Geraldo de Barros, unpublished document, 1979. Thanks to Fabiana de Barros and Michel Favre.

¹⁵ Mammi 2022, p. 12.

¹⁶ Gomringer 2006.

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